

Preparation and Characterisation of Potassium- *bis*(salicylato)diaquotitanium(III) dihydrate and *bis*(salicylato)diaquomanganese(II)

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Potassium *bis*(salicylato)diaquotitanium(III) dihydrate and *bis*(salicylato)diaquomanganese(II) complexes have been prepared by mixing metal hydroxide and aqueous solution of ligand in 1:2 molar ratio. The complexes have been characterised by elemental analysis, derivatographic study (D.T.G., D.T.A., T.G.A.), i.r. spectra measurements, magnetic susceptibility measurements, U.V. and visible reflectance measurements in solid phase. In the case of *bis*(salicylato)diaquomanganese(II) e.s.r. and preliminary X-ray data are also presented.

THE literature survey reveals that the salicylato complexes of many metals including titanium and manganese have been prepared by a number of workers¹⁻⁶ with conflicting results. None of these studies have suggested their structures. In this paper we are reporting the preparation and characterisation of potassium *bis*(salicylato)diaquotitanium(III) dihydrate and *bis*(salicylato)diaquomanganese(II) by derivatographic study, i.r. spectra, magnetic susceptibility and U.V. and visible reflectance measurements in solid phase. In case of Mn-complex e.s.r. and preliminary X-ray diffraction data have also been presented.

Experimental

Methods :

Potassium *bis*(salicylato)diaquotitanium(III) dihydrate was prepared by the interaction of freshly prepared $Ti(OH)_3$ and salicylic acid (1:2 metal ligand ratio). The pH of the solution was adjusted to 6-7 by the addition of dil. KOH solution. *Bis*(salicylato)diaquomanganese(II) was prepared by the interaction of $MnCO_3$ and salicylic acid (1:2 metal ligand ratio). The obtained solution in both the cases was allowed to evaporate in air. After a few days brilliant golden yellow and light buff crystals were obtained respectively in the case of titanium and manganese. The percentage of titanium and manganese was determined as TiO_2 and $MnSO_4$ respectively⁷. Carbon and hydrogen have been estimated by element estimation technique. Potassium was estimated by flame photometer.

Instrumental :

The derivatographic study were made on a system of Paulik, Paulik and Erdey⁸ manufactured by M/s. M.O. M. (Hungarian Optical Works). For D.T.A. ignited alumina has been used as the inert material.

The i.r. spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Model No. 221. Magnetic susceptibility of the complexes were measured on a Gouy balance at room temperature. The spectrophotometric study was carried out on Hilger and Watts Uvispeck spectrophotometer Model No. 700. The silica prism and higher Uvispeck standard reflectance attachment was used to measure the reflectance spectra of the solid complexes. Branker Physic Model BER 402 operated in X-bend using 100 K_c modification frequency was employed for e.s.r. spectra measurements.

For X-ray diffraction analysis good single crystal was selected by observing extinction under a polarised microscope. Oscillation, rotation and Weissenberg photographs were taken with CuK_{α} radiation to determine unit cell, space group and cell contents.

Derivatographic Study :

The combined D.T.G., D.T.A. and T.G.A. study of a sample of 600 mg of potassium *bis*(salicylato)diaquotitanium(III) dihydrate and *bis*(salicylato)diaquomanganese(II) were carried out with heating

Found				Calculated		Calculated			
K	M	C	H	for		K	M	C	H
9.5%	11.01%	38.12%	3.9%	K[Ti(OC ₆ H ₄ COO) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]2H ₂ O		9.05%	11.14%	38.75%	3.71%
	14.98%	45.54%	4.05%	[Mn(OHC ₆ H ₄ COO) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]			15.07%	46.05%	3.84%

rate of 8°/min in static air. The temperature was fixed between 30° to 800°. The summary of the result are in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—POTASSIUM *bis*(SALICYLATO)DIAQUOTITANIUM(III) DIHYDRATE $K[Ti(OC_6H_4COO)_2(H_2O)_2] \cdot 2H_2O$

Position of peak in D.T.G. curve	Compound formed and weight in T.G.A. curve	Nature of peak in D.T.A. curve and position of inflexion point
60°-125°	$K[Ti(OC_6H_4COO)_2(H_2O)_2] \cdot 551$ mg	Endo at 120°
120°-210°	$K[Ti(OC_6H_4COO)_2] \cdot 510$ mg	Endo at 210°
245°-280°	Product not known-485 mg	Endo at 260°
280°-370°	$(K_2CO_3)_x[TiO(OC_6H_4COO)] \cdot 375$ mg	Endo at 315°
		Exo at 335°
370°-460°	$[(K_2CO_3)_x(TiOCO_2)] \cdot 270$ mg	Endo at 425°
460°-640°	$[(K_2CO_3)_xTiO_2] \cdot 215$ mg	Endo at 510°
		Exo at 550°
		Endo at 630°
		Exo at 640°
640°-730°	$[\frac{1}{2}K_2O + TiO_2] \cdot 179$ mg	Endo at 730°
730°-770°	$[KTiO_{1.5}] \cdot 179$ mg	Exo at 770°

TABLE 2—*Bis*(SALICYLATO)DIAQUOMANGANESE(II) $[Mn(OHC_6H_4COO)_2(H_2O)_2]$

Position of peak in D.T.G. curve	Compound formed and weight in T.G.A. curve	Nature of peak in D.T.A. curve and position of inflexion point
135°-185°	$[Mn(OHC_6H_4COO)_2] \cdot 540$ mg	Endo at 170°
240°-320°	$[Mn(OC_6H_4COO)] \cdot 310$ mg	Endo at 290°
330°-510°	$MnCO_3, MnO \cdot 134$ mg	Exo at 375°
		Endo at 500°
510°-670°	$MnO \cdot 115$ mg	Exo
670°-700°	$Mn_2O_4 \cdot 120$ mg	Exo

Endo=Endothermal peak, Exo=Exothermal peak.

I.R. Spectra :

The i.r. spectra of $K[Ti(OC_6H_4COO)_2(H_2O)_2] \cdot 2H_2O$ and $[Mn(OHC_6H_4COO)_2(H_2O)_2]$ were taken in nujol mull. The i.r. spectra of both the complex displays a broad and medium band of 3480-3400 cm^{-1} and 3450-3250 cm^{-1} attributed to $\nu(OH)$ vibration of water molecule. The HOH deformation vibration of water molecule expected near 1600 cm^{-1} is sometimes involved in the strong $\nu(CO)$ vibration of coordinated carboxylic group. A new and medium band in i.r. spectra of almost both the complexes near 810 cm^{-1} suggest the coordination of the water molecule.

The i.r. spectra of $K[Ti(OC_6H_4COO)_2(H_2O)_2] \cdot 2H_2O$ displays $\nu_{as}(CO)$ vibration at 1590 cm^{-1} and $\nu(CO)$ vibration at 1340 cm^{-1} . The splitting of $\nu_{as}(C=O)$ and $\nu_s(C=O)$ could not be located in this complex. The decrease in the i.r. vibration of phenolic(C-OH) 1230 cm^{-1} and $\nu(CO)$ vibration in the complex suggests the bonding of both the

carboxylic oxygen and phenolic oxygen in the complex. The compounds also show two sharp bands at 885 cm^{-1} and 832 cm^{-1} which may be due to Ti-O stretching^{9,10}. A strong band at 632 cm^{-1} may also be attributed to $\nu(Ti-O)$ vibration.

The i.r. spectra of $[Mn(OHC_6H_4COO)_2(H_2O)_2]$ displays the splitting of bands at 1145, 1240 and 1300 cm^{-1} . These indicate the presence of free phenolic-OH.

This is also confirmed by chemical tests. The $\nu_{as}(CO)$ vibration shifts to lower frequency and is observed at 1585 cm^{-1} . The $\nu_s(CO)$ bond due to carboxylate group is found to occur at 1382 cm^{-1} and 1342 cm^{-1} . Thus it is inferred that carboxylate group of coordinated salicylate anion is involved in bidentate bonding through the both oxygen atoms. The phenolic-OH is probably not coordinated to Mn(II) as (C-OH) vibration remains unaffected in the complex.

Magnetic Susceptibility measurements, U.V. and Visible Reflectance spectra and e.s.r. spectra :

The magnetic moment value for $K[Ti(OC_6H_4COO)_2(H_2O)_2] \cdot 2H_2O$ was found to be 1.92 B.M., which corresponds with magnetic moment value for one unpaired spin. This moment value definitely suggests that complex contains Ti in Ti^{3+} state. The magnetic moment value for $[Mn(OHC_6H_4COO)_2(H_2O)_2]$ has been found to be 5.98 B.M. and therefore the complex possesses high spin octahedral environment around manganese(II).

U.V. and visible reflectance spectra was recorded in the region 350 to 1000 nm. In case of $[Ti(OC_6H_4COO)_2(H_2O)_2] \cdot 2H_2O$ no distinct band could be observed rather a shoulder was observed to 460 nm. This band is assigned to ${}^2T_{2g} \rightarrow E_g$ band in octahedral field. $[Mn(OHC_6H_4COO)_2(H_2O)_2]$ did not show any band in this region.

The e.s.r. spectra of the complex $[Mn(OHC_6H_4COO)_2(H_2O)_2]$ was recorded and the g value was calculated to be 2.08 [using D P P H ($g=2.0036$) as a standard]. This g value is expected for six coordinated spin free octahedral manganese(II) complexes.

X-ray Analysis :

The X-ray structure of the compound *bis*(salicylato)diaquomanganese(II) has been investigated. The crystal was found to be monoclinic following cell parameters $a=15.64_6 \text{ \AA}$, $b=12.34_6 \text{ \AA}$, $c=7.26 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha=\gamma=90^\circ$, $\beta=96.9^\circ$. Unit cell volume 1392.28 \AA^3 No. of formulae within the unit cell $Z=4$, Space group $P_{21/C}$. The cell content of the unit cell was calculated from the relation $\rho = \frac{1.66 \times M_z}{V}$

where ρ = density in gm cm^{-3} , M = mol wt of the formula, Z = formula within the unit cell, V = vol of the unit cell in \AA^3 .

The density of the crystal was determined by flotation method using a mixture of bromoform and toluence. The observed density was found to be 1.73 cm^{-3} which gives a volume of unit cell content $Mz = 1451.7$.

The calculated density assuming $Z=4$ comes to be 1.74 cm^{-3} which is in excellent agreement with the observed density.

The unit cell contains four units of the formula $[\text{Mn}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OHCOO})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$. The structure of the compound was determined by three-dimensional X-ray diffraction data by heavy atom technique. The metal ion occupies the space position $0, 0, 0$ and $0, 1/2, 1/2$. Here the metal is linked with six oxygen atoms as shown in figure. The metal and oxygen bond-distance are indicated as below :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Mn-O}_4 &= 2.12 \text{\AA}, \text{ Mn-W}_2 = 2.15, \text{ Mn-O}_2 = 2.13, \\ \text{Mn-O}_6 &= 2.20 \text{\AA}, \text{ Mn-W}_1 = 2.38, \text{ Mn-O}_1 = 2.30 \end{aligned}$$

The X-ray result indicates that in this complex both the O-atom of carboxylic gr. is attached by

metal atom. Phenolic-OH gr. is free, other two oxygens are of water molecule denoted by W_1 and W_2 . The two different molecules are joined by the O-atom of carboxylic group as shown in figure.

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